

MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA XALQARO TAJRIBALAR VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR
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THE ROLE OF NEW INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING
THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: Only a teacher who is highly flexible to the constantly updated changes in the field of education and training for the teaching profession, who knows how to use new information technologies in the educational process, is considered an important person in the formation of personal qualities of a student who is adaptable to changes in society. Currently, the main task in education is to increase the student's interest in each lesson and improve the quality of education and training by learning various methods and new technologies professional training, model of practical training, education, training, personnel, pedagogical, profession, requirements of employers, professional competence

Аннотация: Только преподаватель, обладающий высокой гибкостью к постоянно обновляющимся изменениям в сфере образования и подготовки кадров для педагогической профессии, умеющий использовать новые информационные технологии в образовательном процессе, считается важной персоной в формировании личностных качеств студента, способного адаптироваться к изменениям в обществе. В настоящее время главной задачей в образовании является повышение интереса учащихся к каждому уроку и повышение качества образования и тренинга за счет освоения различных методов и новых технологий

Ключевые слова: профессиональная подготовка, модель практического обучения, образования, подготовки, кадров, педагогической, профессии, требования работодателей, профессиональная компетентность.

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Only a teacher who is highly flexible to the constantly updated changes in the field of education and training for the teaching profession, who knows how to use new information technologies in the educational process, is considered an important person in the formation of personal qualities of a student who is adaptable to changes in society. Currently, the main task in education is to increase the student's interest in each lesson and improve the quality of education and training by learning various methods and new technologies. A well-chosen innovation should guarantee that a high-quality new introduction becomes a source of income. By innovative process, we mean a full-fledged action on discovery, acquisition, application and comprehensive distribution of news. Now we can consider the creation of new scientific and practical knowledge and their acquisition and implementation from an innovative point of view.

New information technologies are fundamentally connected with the educational process, teacher's and student's actions, its structure, used tools, methods and approaches. Mastering new technology requires great skill, special training and research, literacy and responsibility from the teacher. In addition to deepening knowledge, innovative teaching leads students to learning activities and increases their enthusiasm and interest in learning. Every teacher should be able to use the new technology in accordance with the current era of globalization according to his convenience and subject. It is necessary to transform and enliven each lesson in order to make each subject attractive and to increase students' interest in learning. For that reason, it is not preferable to use a variety of technological elements rather than being limited to one technology. During the lesson, the main goal of problem-based learning technology is to teach students to search independently, to develop their knowledge and creativity. The technology of the educational process is a system of goals, content, tools, forms and methods focused on the development of the student's personality. At present, the transition to the national model of education has mastered the latest innovative pedagogical technologies, mastered the psychological and pedagogical theory, has the ability to quickly get rid of the old pattern formed in the educational process, and has the flexibility to create its own

concrete path in real practical activities. It is necessary to become a teacher-researcher, a thinking teacher. The great thinker, scholar al-Farabi, said, "The greatest quality in a person is the ability to understand life, contentment, determination and unique individuality." It is possible to make sure that this life position of the scholar is the main harmony of today's knowledge. Pedagogical technology deals with the creation of an advanced teaching and educational system and the design of the educational process. Pedagogical technology forms a system of scientifically based practical methods that ensure the solution of the main goals and tasks of education, with the aim of designing a renewable educational process controlled by pedagogical technology.

Effectiveness of pedagogical technology depends on pedagogical conditions. Pedagogical conditions include, first of all, the personal characteristics of the teacher: personality, culture, curiosity, etc. can be attributed. At the same time, the competence and professional skills of communicating with students will be of special importance. It is possible to conduct a lesson using many types of new pedagogical technologies.

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